

Mechanism of Acid-catalysed Oxidation of Lactic Acid by Vanadium(v)—An Application of Bunnett Criterion

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The mechanism of acid-catalysed oxidation of lactic acid by vanadium(v) has been reinvestigated and the role of water in the rate-determining step as a nucleophile has been established on the basis of Bunnett hypothesis and Bunnett-Olsen L.F.E.R.

A survey of the literature¹ reveals that the effect of acidity function on the oxidation of hydroxy-acids by vanadium(v) was observed by Jones *et al.*². They could satisfactorily explain the rate of acid-dependent oxidation on the basis of Zucker-Hammett hypothesis^{3,4} and derived the following rate expression,

$$-\frac{d[V^V]}{dt} = k[S][V^V][1 + ah_0] \quad (1)$$

Later the Zucker-Hammett hypothesis was sharply criticised^{5,6} and then, Bunnett^{7,8} and Bunnett and Olsen⁹ suggested some empirical, yet quite useful, relationship and criterion for the classification of acid-catalysed reactions. This has been applied to the acid-catalysed oxidation of lactic acid by vanadium(v) to investigate the role of water, if any, in the rate-limiting step.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR and G.R. grades. Double-distilled water was used to prepare all solutions. The reactants were kept in a thermostat ($\pm 0.1^\circ$) before the final mixing. The kinetics of the reaction were followed spectrophotometrically observing the formation of vanadium(IV). First order dependence was observed with respect to lactic acid and vanadium(v) concentrations. The effect of concentration of acid (HClO_4) on the rate was observed in the moderately concentrated region (1.30–6.06 M). The results are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF HClO_4 ON RATE OF OXIDATION OF LACTIC ACID BY VANADIUM(V)

$[V^V] = 3.93 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, $[\text{Lactic acid}] = 0.20 \text{ M}$, $\text{Temp.} = 25 \pm 0.1^\circ$

$[\text{HClO}_4]$ M	k_1 $\times 10^4 \text{ s}^{-1}$	$-H_0$	$-\log a_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$
1.30	1.39	0.44	0.025
2.25	2.61	0.90	0.050
3.19	5.20	1.36	0.089
4.12	13.93	1.80	0.140
5.06	31.66	2.26	0.215
6.06	66.60	2.86	0.330

Results and Discussion

Jones *et al.*² derived the following expression for the dependence of rate of oxidation on the concentration of hydrogen ions in $\text{HClO}_4 - \text{NaClO}_4$ mixtures of constant ionic strength,

$$k = k_0[1 + ah_0][\alpha\text{-hydroxy acid}] \quad (2)$$

whereby an acid-independent and -dependent reactions are indicated. The following mechanism was suggested,

The Zucker-Hammett plots [$\log(k/k_0)$ vs $-H_0$] in oxidation of lactic acid by V^V exhibit a linear relationship (slope = 0.92). Such linear plots with slopes deviating from the ideal slope of unity are not uncommon⁶⁻⁹. In view of this deviation, Bunnett hypothesis was tested. A plot of $\log k_1 + H_0$ vs $-\log a_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ and $\log k_1 - \log [\text{HClO}_4]$ vs $-\log a_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ gave the value of ω and ω^* equal to 1.94 and -4.16, respectively, indicating the participation of a molecule of water as a nucleophile in the rate-limiting step. This observation is further supported by the slope value $\phi = 1.90$ (Bunnett-Olsen L.F.E.R.⁹) and is consistent with the following transition state which involves an $\text{S}_{\text{N}}2$ character¹⁰.

This would however not explain (i) the dissolution of ammonium metavanadate in lactic acid (and

in other α -hydroxy acids as well), (ii) the order of reactivity^{11,12}, mandelic > glycollic $\geq$ lactic > α -hydroxyisobutyric acids and (iii) the observed ω and ω^* values. The removal of α -H as hydride ion should have negative ω value as has been observed in many representative cases involving the formation of carbonium ions. The observed ω value does not accord with this proposal. In fact, nucleophilic participation of water would offset the formation of carbonium ions (negative ω value) resulting in lowering of ω value as observed by Venkatasubramanian *et al.*¹³ in the oxidation of lactic acid by chromic acid. This of course is a very subtle question and one can not know as to what extent the incipient carbonium ion has dissipated its positive charge to the nucleophile (water), which does seem to affect ω values. Nevertheless, the value of ω can not turn out to be positive as observed here.

Mechanism suggested by Jones *et al.*² implies C-C bond fission leading to the formation of acetaldehyde. The latter under experimental conditions reacts too slow to yield acetic acid. Hence, a quantitative yield of acetaldehyde should be expected. The product studies suggest very little C-C bond rupture to yield acetaldehyde¹⁴. The major part of the reaction proceeds via pyruvic acid formation, which does react much faster than acetaldehyde under experimental conditions. Obviously the mechanism suggested by Jones *et al.*² does not represent the complete reaction as a major part of the reaction occurs via C-H bond rupture. If the role of water molecules as a nucleophile is not restricted to the attack on incipient carbonium ions, then one could envisage an acetoin type of oxidation, wherein the nucleophile, H₂O, removes α -H as a proton¹⁵.

This would reconcile with most of the facts observed so far on the oxidation of α -hydroxy acids by vanadium(V).

If the nucleophilic participation of water molecule be taken in its original sense⁷⁻⁹, then one can think of a transition state involving the removal of oxygen $2P\pi$ electrons to the $3d$ -orbitals on vana-

dium, which is facilitated by the nucleophilic attack of water molecule on the carbon developing the double bond character. Thus

The transition state is consistent with the proposals made earlier^{16,17}.

The coordination of alcoholic OH to V^V and the subsequent removal of electrons from oxygen of OH would render H of OH more acidic, thereby increasing the extent of solvation of the transition state. This would also polarise α -C-H bond and cause greater solvation of the transition state as compared to the reactants. This is in conformity with the hydration change theory of ω values^{7,8}.

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